

Recent Advances in Resin Flow Simulations in Liquid Composite Molding Processes

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SUMMARY

The modeling approach to accommodate the variations in material data and the infusion process in Liquid Composite Molding process will be presented. Dual scale flow, resin redistribution after the injection is discontinued and material and preforming variability will be addressed. Examples to design more robust injection schemes will be demonstrated.

Keywords: Mold Filling, Resin Flow, Composites, Modeling and Simulation, Resin Injection, Fiber Tow Saturation

INTRODUCTION

In Liquid Composite Molding (LCM), a fibrous preform is placed into a mold. A thermosetting resin is then introduced through injection gates to cover all the empty spaces between the fibers. Once the resin reaches the vent, the injection is discontinued. The composite part is de-molded after the resin cures. There are several variations of this process, most widely known are the Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) and the Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) process. In all LCM processes, the stationary preform must be completely saturated with resin during the injection. For non-trivial parts, experience or intuition is not sufficient to anticipate the resin flow patterns, required pressure or filling time. Trial and error approaches are expensive and do not lead themselves to robust process design. Flow simulations can be employed to address this technological gap.

LCM MODELING

To simulate the mold filling, the flow of resin through fiber preforms is modeled as flow through anisotropic porous media. A finite element/control volume (FE/CV) solution scheme is used to simulate the filling process [1]. The solution domain is meshed with a fixed finite element mesh. Control volumes are associated with each mesh node or alternatively every element. Pressure is solved at each node, flow rates are computed and the flowfront is advanced by explicit integration in time domain in which the time

step is selected so as to fill at least one additional control volume and change the fluid domain. Boundary conditions can be updated at each time step. This allows one to simulate mold filling as well as address variations in process physics or preform architecture as a function of time and thus model any LCM process.

FIBER TOW SATURATION AND MICROVOIDS

Dual scale nature of the fiber preforms is addressed by attaching one dimensional elements to each node of the mesh. Its properties are matched to fiber tow permeability, which is usually much lower than the bulk permeability, and fiber tow dimensions. This allows us to track the macroflow and the saturation of the fiber tows. Unfilled or partially filled tows may be detected, allowing us to predict the microvoids. A characterization method is used to determine bulk as well as equivalent tow permeability from a single experiment.

MATERIAL AND PROCESS VARIABILITY

The material characterization for LCM flow modeling provides a range of values, rather than a “universal” permeability constant. The source of this variability may be partially due to minor variation in fabric architecture, due to manual cutting and placing of the fabric in the mold and due to layering and “nesting” of the fabrics together to form the multi-layered reinforcement and is usually unpredictable. The issue is compounded when significant local permeability changes can occur around the inserts and along the edges and corners due to poor preform cutting, inaccurate placement and by the preform failure to conform to the mold surface, particularly around sharp corners. All these local variations will modify the resin filling patterns possibly changing the last place reached by resin (the desirable vent location). These effects may cause failure of the filling process if either the resin gels before the injection is complete or if the resin reaches the vent location before the regions between the fiber tows and within the fiber tows are saturated.

Our approach focuses on designing the injection scheme in a way that makes the process robust and can saturate the preform with the resin despite the variability. The intent is to create an injection scheme which can lead to successful filling for the widest possible range of parameters. This may require slowing the resin injection, placing the inlets in strategic locations and creating additional vacuum vents in the mold. [2]. To create a robust process, either with passive or active control, we simulate under program control rather than a manual procedure of trial and modify scheme the filling for many permutations and from the results present a methodology for a robust process design [3].

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